

DOES THE SPOUSE MATTER? A SCOPING REVIEW ON SPOUSAL SUPPORT FOR WORKING POPULATION

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history:</p> <p>Received 20 February 2023</p> <p>Accepted 18 May 2023</p>	<p>Purpose: The review aims to discover and report the literature on spousal support provided to working population (men/women) and the predictors, outcomes, mediators and moderators found in relation to spousal support.</p>
<p>Keywords:</p> <p>Spousal Support; Review; Working; Employed; Spouse; Professional.</p>	<p>Theoretical Framework: Support at home (or spousal support) is vital for a married men or women so that they can invest more energy at work. The concept is proposed and supported by a number of theories, such as spousal support theory, human capital theory, and was utilized to choose only working population for this review.</p>
	<p>Design/Methodology/Approach: A scoping review research model was used to systematically search for and report the empirical literature on spousal support in context of working population. Scopus database was used to search for literature on the topic, with no limit on time and discipline of publication. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) flow diagram for scoping review was used to show the search and filtering process used.</p>
	<p>Findings: A total of 706 empirical articles were obtained from Scopus database, out of which 699 articles were removed while matching the title and abstract of literature with selection criteria. Further, 149 articles were excluded because of incompatibility of full text article with eligibility criteria, this left us with 61 articles to be reviewed on the topic of interest.</p>
	<p>Research, Practical & Social implications: This study aimed to examine spousal support among working population (men and women) and its associated predictors, outcomes, mediators and moderators.</p>
	<p>Originality/Value: In the past, review has been conducted on spousal support but no effort was made to look for study characteristics, sample characteristics, or detailed methodological features, especially in context of working population. Hence, the present review will be first to give an initial idea on the way spousal support has been described, measured, the country where and when the topic has been studied most and other sample and methodology related choices.</p>
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O CÔNJUGE É IMPORTANTE? UMA ANÁLISE DE ESCOPO SOBRE O APOIO DO CÔNJUGE PARA A POPULAÇÃO TRABALHADORA

RESUMO

Objetivo: A revisão tem como objetivo descobrir e relatar a literatura sobre o apoio conjugal fornecido à população trabalhadora (homens/mulheres) e os preditores, resultados, mediadores e moderadores encontrados em relação ao apoio conjugal.

Estrutura teórica: O apoio em casa (ou apoio do cônjuge) é vital para que homens e mulheres casados possam investir mais energia no trabalho. O conceito é proposto e apoiado por várias teorias, como a teoria do apoio conjugal, a teoria do capital humano, e foi utilizado para escolher apenas a população trabalhadora para esta análise.

Projeto/Metodologia/Abordagem: Um modelo de pesquisa de revisão de escopo foi usado para pesquisar e relatar sistematicamente a literatura empírica sobre apoio conjugal no contexto da população trabalhadora. O banco de dados Scopus foi usado para pesquisar a literatura sobre o tópico, sem limite de tempo e disciplina de publicação. O diagrama de fluxo do Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) para revisão de escopo foi usado para mostrar o processo de pesquisa e filtragem utilizado.

Resultados: Um total de 706 artigos empíricos foi obtido do banco de dados Scopus, dos quais 699 artigos foram removidos durante a correspondência do título e do resumo da literatura com os critérios de seleção. Além disso, 149 artigos foram excluídos devido à incompatibilidade do texto completo do artigo com os critérios de elegibilidade, o que nos deixou com 61 artigos a serem revisados sobre o tópico de interesse.

Implicações sociais, práticas e de pesquisa: Este estudo teve como objetivo examinar o apoio conjugal entre a população trabalhadora (homens e mulheres) e seus preditores, resultados, mediadores e moderadores associados.

Originalidade/valor: No passado, foi realizada uma revisão sobre o apoio conjugal, mas não foi feito nenhum esforço para procurar características do estudo, características da amostra ou características metodológicas detalhadas, especialmente no contexto da população trabalhadora. Portanto, a presente revisão será a primeira a dar uma ideia inicial sobre a forma como o apoio conjugal foi descrito, medido, o país onde e quando o tópico foi mais estudado e outras escolhas relacionadas à amostra e à metodologia.

Palavras-chave: Apoio Conjugal, Revisão, Trabalho, Empregado, Cônjuge, Profissional.

¿IMPORTA EL CÓNJUGE? UN ANÁLISIS EXHAUSTIVO DE LA AYUDA CONYUGAL A LA POBLACIÓN ACTIVA

RESUMEN

Objetivo: La revisión tiene como objetivo descubrir e informar sobre la bibliografía relativa al apoyo del cónyuge a la población trabajadora (hombres/mujeres) y los predictores, resultados, mediadores y moderadores encontrados en relación con el apoyo del cónyuge.

Marco teórico: El apoyo en el hogar (o apoyo conyugal) es vital para que los hombres y mujeres casados inviertan más energía en el trabajo. Este concepto está propuesto y apoyado por varias teorías, como la teoría del apoyo conyugal y la teoría del capital humano, y se utilizó para elegir sólo a la población trabajadora para este análisis.

Diseño/Metodología/Enfoque: Se utilizó un modelo de investigación de revisión exhaustiva para buscar e informar sistemáticamente sobre la literatura empírica sobre el apoyo conyugal en el contexto de la población trabajadora. Se utilizó la base de datos Scopus para buscar bibliografía sobre el tema, sin límite de tiempo ni disciplina de publicación. Se utilizó el diagrama de flujo de los Elementos de Información Preferidos para la Revisión Sistemática (PRISMA) para la revisión del alcance con el fin de mostrar el proceso de búsqueda y filtrado utilizado.

Resultados: Se obtuvo un total de 706 artículos empíricos de la base de datos Scopus, de los cuales se eliminaron 699 artículos al cotejar el título y el resumen de la literatura con los criterios de selección. Además, 149 artículos fueron excluidos debido a la incompatibilidad del texto completo del artículo con los criterios de elegibilidad, dejándonos con 61 artículos para ser revisados sobre el tema de interés.

Implicaciones sociales, prácticas y de investigación: Este estudio tuvo como objetivo examinar el apoyo marital entre la población trabajadora (hombres y mujeres) y sus predictores, resultados, mediadores y moderadores asociados.

Originalidad/valor: En el pasado se ha realizado una revisión sobre el apoyo marital, pero no se ha hecho ningún esfuerzo por buscar las características del estudio, las características de la muestra o las características metodológicas detalladas, especialmente en el contexto de la población trabajadora. Por lo tanto, la presente revisión será la primera en dar una idea inicial sobre cómo se ha descrito y medido el apoyo conyugal, el país donde y cuándo se ha estudiado más el tema y otras opciones relacionadas con la muestra y la metodología.

Palabras clave: Apoyo Conyugal, Revisión, Trabajo, Empleado, Cónyuge, Profesional.

INTRODUCTION

A strong career inclination among women worldwide has increased the number of families with dual-earners, which brings definite challenges of constantly balancing between work and family life for these working women/men (Abele & Volmer, 2011; Madraswale & Velmurugan, 2023; Sivasankaran & Selvkrishnan, 2023). To enable their success while managing work and family domain, social support is believed to be a crucial resource (Marcinkus et al., 2007). Taking from Thoits (1995) and Winnubst (1993), social support is defined as the positive, emotionally sustaining quality of relationship that typically involves receiving care, encouragement, advice and material aid from others during stressful times. There is a growing consensus that sources (i.e., the one who provides support) of social support can be work-based or personal (non-work) based. Work-based social support may be provided by the employee's organization, immediate supervisors and co-workers, whereas, personal (non-work) social support is offered by employee's spouse or partner, children, siblings, neighbours, community, parents and friends (Marcinkus et al., 2007). Out of various sources of support mentioned, spousal support (i.e., the social support provided by the spouse) is concurred to be the most significant sources of social support in career progression (Noor, 2002; Ezzedeen & Ritchey, 2008; Narayanan & Barnabas, 2020). Such support encompasses understanding and motivating in ongoing career advancement, splitting the household and parenting liabilities and providing interpersonal support to the other partner (Gordon & Whelan-Berry, 2004).

Around 1970s, when the discussion of social support was initiated in relation to spouse, the main aim was to show the effect of having a wife on managerial career of men (Ahmed & Carrim, 2016; Heikkinen, 2014). Spousal support theory of Kanter (1977) suggested that married men have a supplementary resource in the form of wives, particularly wives who are not working, to manage household responsibilities including childcare and to assist husband with any work-related issue (Heikkinen, 2014). This provides married men more time and energy to invest in work in comparison to any single men. Whereas, in case of married women the same theory proposes that married women will not flourish in their career as much as a single woman will, because they will have household responsibilities and will not get similar support as a married man (Ahmed & Carrim, 2016). Thus, majority of studies focuses on spousal support received by working women and we are expecting to see the same trend in this review.

Literature has categorized social support in a number of ways, such as emotional, instrumental, appraisal and informational support (House, 1981) or informational support, instrumental support, esteem support and social companionship (Cohen and Wills, 1985). But the best and most common way is to categorize it into two: instrumental and emotional support (Beehr, 1985). The same classifications have been adopted in literature while categorizing spousal support. Even conceptualization and operationalization of social/spousal support has happened in a number of different ways in the literature (Polk, 2008).

From preliminary review of available systematic literature review on the subject, it is evident that literature on spousal support has been reviewed in the past, but most of them examined spousal support for psychologically ill (e.g., Antoniou et al., 2021; Antoniou et al., 2022) or physically ill (e.g., Thompson et al., 2020; Albanese et al., 2019) or pregnant spouse (e.g., Roye & Balk, 1996) or for smoking cessation of spouse (Hemsing et al., 2012). These reviews do not necessarily focus on working population and even those targeted towards working class, has reported about literature on spousal support for women entrepreneurs (Wolf & Frese, 2018) and on relationship between partner support and work-family interface (Kelley et al., 2021). To the best of our knowledge, no systematic literature review has been conducted on spousal support in context with everyday hassles of working population. Similar result was obtained from COCHRANE and PROSPERO databases for systematic literature review performed in August, 2022. A decision for studying everyday hassles of working population has been made based on the views of Cutrona (1996) and Vaux (1988) about social support that it is about everyday actions taken which shows actions and concern. Moreover, no literature review on spousal support (with working or non-working population) was found where study characteristics, sample characteristics and methodological features of spousal support has been reviewed in detail.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the present review of literature, only those studies were included where they have discussed about spousal support provided to working population (men/women) in context of managing everyday struggle of work and personal life. Spousal support provided to working/non-working population in relation to the work-related issues or sickness or in any other specific concern of life (such as pregnancy) were all excluded from the study. Spouse providing the support can be employed (or from dual-earner family) or can be unemployed.

Articles with views on spousal support provided to working population were included, irrespective of the fact that those views are taken from receiver or provider.

Aim of the Review

The main aim of review is to identify and synthesize the existing literature on reported level of spousal support among working class and the factors influencing or being influenced by spousal support.

To be more specific, review answers following research questions:

1. First, how spousal support has been conceptualized (definition) and measured (operational definition) in the available literature for working class?
2. Second, what theories have been used by researchers to explain spousal support?
3. Third, which antecedents, moderators, mediators and consequences of spousal support are common? Which constructs are mediated or moderated by spousal support?
4. Fourth, what methodological choices have been used in the available literature?

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

A scoping review of available literature about spousal support for working population was conducted and implemented as outlined by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Scoping review was chosen as most appropriate technique as it is designed to map the key evidence available in any given area, which has not been extensively explored before (Mays et al., 2001). Also, unlike systematic review, a scoping study rarely target specific research questions and is not answered from relatively exclusive list of quality assessed research studied (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005). The conditions fit with the present study and therefore was found suitable. Methodological framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005) for conducting scoping review consists of five stages discussed below.

Stage I: Identifying the Research Question

Opening step of a scoping review is suggested to recognize a research question which is broad enough to reproduce significant literature on the topic of interest, and embrace the concerned population, outcomes and topic. Hence, the previously given research question was framed.

Stage II: Identifying the Relevant Studies to the Particular Research Questions

In this stage appropriate databases and keywords were identified to acquire relevant studies. This stage has two phases:

First, a search of COCHRANE and PROSPERO databases was conducted which showed that no significant reviews have been registered or completed on the topic of interest. An initial search of systematic reviews on spousal support has been conducted in relevant databases (e.g., Scopus, Google Scholar) to identify a comprehensive list of search terms from the literature (systematic reviews) on spousal support with population other than working class (Haber et al., 2007). Secondly, similar to Margherita (2020) and Kim et al., (2020) main literature search was conducted on Scopus database using following Boolean terms in title, abstract or keywords field: “Spousal support” OR “spouse support” OR “partner support” OR “marital support” OR “husbands Support” OR “husband support” OR “wife support” OR “wives support” OR “life partner support” OR “life partners support” OR “domestic partner support” OR “spousal influence” OR “spouse’s role” OR “spouse role” OR “spousal resources” OR “spousal caregiving” OR “spouse involvement” OR “spousal involvement” OR “partner social support” OR “support from spouse” AND “working” OR “employ*” OR “career*” OR “professional*” OR “executive*” OR “manager*” OR “work-family” OR “work and family” OR “family-work” OR “family and work” OR “family-life” OR “dual career” OR “dual-career” OR “dual-earner” OR “dual earner” OR “two career” OR “two-career”

Second half of search terms were used to limit our search results to working population but no limitation was applied for the year or place of publication, discipline and document type. We took the advice of Ortenblad (2010) while incorporating search terms to get more exhaustive list of articles on topic and therefore used other terms similar to spousal support as well. Moreover, Scopus database was selected as it is often considered to cover wide range of topics in comparison to other famous databases (Abbas *et al.*, 2022). Using search terms given above in Scopus database yielded 706 papers until September 2022.

Stage III: Study Selection

In this stage, selection/eligibility criteria were created (see Table 1) and each article found on the topic was checked to assess fit of their objective with the selection criteria formed.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<p><u>Method</u>: Searching the title and abstract of the article <u>Source</u>: Scopus database <u>Period</u>: Until September 2022 <u>Geographical limit</u>: Worldwide <u>Language</u>: English only <u>Publication</u>: Published in a peer-reviewed journal. <u>Research Design</u>: Empirical (qualitative, quantitative or mixed-method research design). <u>Content and Population type</u>: Moderately or highly relevant to spousal support in working population; the support offered should be received by working population and offered by working or non-working spouse (dual-earner families or otherwise).</p>	<p>Any study which is not published in peer reviewed journals (such as conference abstracts, book chapter), Not empirical (such as review or meta-analysis), Articles which are focused on spousal support but support is not for dealing with everyday hassles of working population at work and home (e.g., support while pregnancy, sickness, work-related support and such), the one receiving the support is from non-working population, Studies where sample was unemployed or unmarried or not in a regular relationship were removed, Studies which mention spousal support only as recommendation or in their discussion or conclusion were removed.</p>

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

In the review, only those studies were selected which manifest all the inclusion criteria and indicate absence of the exclusion criteria. Selection of studies involved a number of stages and followed the process of Joanna Briggs Institute’s PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis) for scoping review in the search process (Figure 1).

At first, references of obtained documents (706) were recorded in Mendeley reference manager, followed by removal of duplicate studies (n= 7) which gave 699 articles. In line with previous articles (Murray & Graybeal, 2007 and Bowen & Swift, 2017), the title and abstract of remaining 699 articles were screened against eligibility criteria specified before and as a result 540 studies were excluded and 149 included. This stage is called as preselection in some cases (Bowen & Swift, 2017). Following previous review articles published in reputed journals (Foss & Saebi, 2017; Kossek & Ozeki, 1998 and Saebi et al., 2019) articles published only in peer reviewed journal were included and conference paper, book chapter or editorial notes were removed. Purposefully, studies using all type of research design (quantitative, qualitative and mixed) were allowed to be included to give a wider knowledge based on the topic of interest (Rousseau, et al., 2008). It should be noted that the studies screened in (149) was either found eligible to be a part of this review article, or abstract and title of studies were unable to provide clear information necessary for answering eligibility questions (Nolan & Garavan, 2015). In either case, attempt was made for full text of 149 articles.

Next, complete texts of 149 articles were assessed against the eligibility criteria specified in Table 1. As a result, 97 documents were removed and 61 articles were kept for

main review (Murray & Graybeal, 2007). This stage is known as selection in some cases (Bowen & Swift, 2017). Out of 97 excluded documents, 8 were removed as their full text was not available, 2 were not in English and 1 was review article. Further, 61 and 25 articles were removed as they were incompatible with content and population required, respectively. Reasons for exclusion are mentioned below in the box.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram for literature search and study selection

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

In both the given stages, preselection and selection, two authors independently assessed the fit of research articles and disagreements between reviewers was being solved through discussions (Kim et al., 2020).

Stage IV: Charting the Data

This stage of scoping review involves charting or extracting key information from studies finally selected for review (n=61). The information to be extracted depends on the research questions of that particular systematic review. In our case, we extracted data on study characteristics (authors, year of publication, journal name, aim, industry, country of data collection, type of article), definition of spousal support, alternative terms used for spousal support, theories adopted, antecedents, consequences, mediator, moderator and mediation moderation of spousal support, spousal support as mediator, moderator and moderator-mediator, suggested relation for qualitative study, sample characteristics (sample and sample size, focus of spousal support in sample, sampling method, paradigm), measures and number of items of measures, data collection method, analytical technique and interview domain for qualitative study. In line with Saeb et al. (2019), for qualitative studies, interview domain and suggested relation of spousal support with any other variable was recorded.

Stage V: Collating, Summarising and Reporting the Results

In this stage, obtained data will be summarized and reported in form of table or graphs. Unlike systematic review, scoping review do not assess quality of evidence and hence present an overview of all material reviewed which makes presenting the large data an issue of concern (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005). This stage will be fully represented in the next section, that is result of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ultimately, sixty-one articles were included in the review. The study characteristics of the selected articles are first described, followed by findings dedicated to four research questions of this review article. Following Bianchi and Milkie (2010), articles were divided as highly relevant (n= 30) and moderately relevant (n=31). Such marking was based on the focus of the study, if spousal support is addressed as core topic that study will fall under highly relevant. Whereas if spousal support is mentioned but not as core topic of discussion then that study was marked as moderately relevant.

Study Characteristics

Study characteristics of included 61 articles are summarized in supplementary documents (can be obtained from first author). Out of 61 articles, 47 of them were quantitative, 12 were qualitative and 2 used quantitative as well as qualitative but were not mixed method. Of particular note is that 21 articles (34%) included USA in their data collection, followed by South Africa and Finland (n = 5 each), Israel (n=4), Canada, Turkey (n = 3 each), China, India, Hong Kong, Switzerland and Netherland (n=2 each). Two articles did not report the country of data collection. In case of years of publication, no significant trend was noticed. From the relevant studies acquired, first publication on the topic of interest took place in 1984 and maximum number of publications (n = 5) was in 2020. Maximum number of articles (n = 7) were found to be published in Journal of Vocational Behaviour, followed by Sex Roles, Marriage and Family Review and Journal of Family Issues (n= 3 each), Current Psychology, Journal of Community Psychology, Journal of Family and Economic Issues, Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, Journal of Organizational Behaviour, Women in Management Review (n = 3 each). The included articles on spousal support focused mainly on academia/education and healthcare/hospital (n = 7 each), 16 articles collected data from multiple industries and 25 articles failed to report the type of industry they surveyed on. This study recorded the alternative terms used in studies for spousal support, where the content or meaning is similar to spousal support but the term used is different. It was realized that majority of studies (n = 51) used spousal support, 5 of them used spouse role/spouse support role, 3 used partner support and 1 used husband support and spousal support communication practices. This result can help future studies to be more confident using the term ‘spousal/spouse support’ along with other terms mentioned before, while deciding the keywords if the topic of interest is spousal support.

Conceptualization (or Definition) and Operationalization (or Measures) of Spousal Support (Research question 1)

To answer first research question about definition of and how spousal support was measured or operationalized in the reviewed articles, spousal support is categorized by the type of support covered by concept of interest in various studies (Jolly et al., 2017). In line with previous work (Le et al., 2020), in case of operationalization, measurement scale and number of items (single/multiple) used was recorded and reported.

As seen in Table 2, the most common type of support used in the studies are emotional (n =23) and instrumental (n =24) support, followed by career related support and child care support (n =7), financial support (n =5), informational support (n =4), interpersonal and attitudinal support (n =2). In 22 studies, spousal support had no clear definition, that means those studies did not discuss about the kind of support they covered.

Table 2: Conceptualization (or Definition) of Spousal support in the Reviewed Articles

Definition of Spousal support	Studies cited	Percentage	Example of Studies
Number of studies without a clear definition	22	21	Davoine E. et al. (2013), Bowen P. and Zhang R.P. (2020), Heikkinen, S.S. (2014).
Emotional support	23	22	Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013), Irak, U. D. (2020), Suchet M. and Barling J. (1986).
Instrumental/Procedural/Physical support/Housework/Household management/Division of chores	24	23	Irak, U. D. (2020), Karapinar P. B., et al. (2020), Rosenbaum M. and Cohen E. (1999).
Attitudinal support	2	1.9	Kim J.L.S. and Ling C. S. (2001)
Childcare	7	6.7	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Wani A.K. (2022).
Career related/Support for work/support as employee	7	6.7	Bhowon U. et al. (2008), Steffy B.D. and Ashbaugh D. (1986).
Informational	4	3.8	Amin S. et al. (2017)
Financial	5	4.8	Zheng X. et al. (2022)
Interpersonal support	2	1.9	Edwards M.R. (2006)
Spousal support on that particular day, encouraging discussion, acceptance, dialogue and assistance, time, decision, technical and network support, support received and provided, moral support, maintaining marital relationship, consensus in family matters, sexual satisfaction.	1	7.6	Pluut H. et al. (2018), Syrotuik J. and D'Arcy C. (1984).

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

In the reviewed article, one scale which is quite common (n=7) is Family Support Inventory Scale given by King et al. (1995) (Table 3). Parasuraman et al. (1992) spousal support scale was used by 2 studies and 17 studies either used self-made scale or they did not report the scale used for measurement. All the scales used were multi-item, that means had two or more than two items in scale for measuring spousal support.

Table 3: Operationalization (or Measures) of Spousal Support in Reviewed Articles

Scales used	Single/Multi-item	Studies cited	Example of studies
Self-made or not reported	Not reported	17	Steffy B.D. and Ashbaugh D. (1986), Zheng X. et al. (2022), Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2006), Pluut H. et al. (2018).

Family Support Inventory Scale, King et al. (1995)	Multi-item (all studies)	9	Irak, U. D. (2020), Karapinar P. B., et al. (2020), Aycan Z. and Eskin M. (2005).
Parasuraman et al. (1992)	Multi-item (All studies)	2	Ocampo A.C.G. et al. (2018).
Career/Marital Stress of Women Inventory (CMSWI), Vinokur and Van Ryn (1993), Caplan et al. (1980), Cohen and Wills, (1985), Daalen et al's (2006), House (1981), ISSB, Barrera (1981), Kupsch et al. (2009), Mills, et al. (1992), Baruch and Barnett's (1986), Schuster et al. (1990) scale, Tovel (1984), Walen and Lachman (2000), Selvarajan et al. (2013), Spousal Support Scale (Buffardi & Erdwins, 1997), Verhofstadt et al., (2013), Matsui et al., (1995), Frone & Yardley, (1996), Marshall and Rossman, (1999), Strauss and Corbin (1990), Schieman and Young (2013) and (in a modified form) by Bowen et al. (2018), Friedman and Greenhaus (2000).	Multi-item (All studies)	1	Phillips-Miller D.L. et al. (2000), Lee N.Y. et al. (2014), Polk D.M. (2008), Westman M. and Da Lia E. (2005), O'Brien K.M. et al. (2014), Gordon J.R. and Whelan-Berry K.S. (2004).

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

Theoretical Framework for Spousal Support (Research Question 2)

To report the theories utilized to explain spousal support, categorization of available studies as highly and moderately relevant were used. The reason behind using the categorization here is that studies marked as highly relevant (HR) will be in better position than moderately relevant (MR), as highly relevant main focus is spousal support. However, Conservation of Resource theory (n=4, HR and n =3, MR) and Boundary theory (n=3, HR and n=1, MR) was distinctly mentioned in both the categories (MR and HR). It is to be noted that two studies in HR used spousal support theory to explain spousal support. Report in this section was influenced by Le et al. (2020).

Table 4: Theories used in Reviewed Studies of Spousal Support

Theories	Study Cited	Percentage	Example of Studies
Highly relevant			
Not reported	19	53	Aycan Z. and Eskin M. (2005), Wani A.K. (2022), Ezzedeem S.R. and Ritchey K.G. (2008)

Conservation of Resource Theory	4	11	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2012), Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2010).
Boundary Theory	3	8	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2012)
Spousal support theory	2	5.5	Ahmed S.F. and Carrim N.M.H. (2016)
Hobfoll's stress theory, Role prioritization theory, Role Theory, Marriage contract and psychological contract theory and Gender Role Ideology, Integrative Model of Work family interface, Constructivist and Humanistic theories of communication, Goffman's dramaturgical approach, Spillover theory	1	22.2	Rosenbaum M. and Cohen E. (1999), Nikina A. et al. (2015), Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013).
Moderately relevant			
Not clear/not reported	19	57	Ray J.A. (1988), Parasuraman S. et al. (1992), Syrotuik J. and D'Arcy C. (1984)
Conservation of Resource theory	3	9	Halbesleben J.R.B. (2010), Wang B. et al. (2021).
Boundary theory, Cohen and Wills (1985), Family-to-work positive spillover, Model of proactive motivation, Near et al.'s (1980) model of the interdependence, Role balance theory, social support, Spillover and Crossover, Transaction stress, Work home resources.	1	30	Zhang R.P. and Bowen P. (2021), Matsui T. et al. (1995), Lee N.Y. et al. (2014).

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

Antecedents, Moderators, Mediators and Consequences of Spousal Support and Spousal support as Moderator or Mediator (Research Question 3)

Quantitative studies

In Table 5, they have reported antecedents, consequences/outcomes, mediator and moderator (for quantitative studies) related to spousal support in reviewed articles for this study. Whereas, Table 6 shows the moderating and mediating effect of spousal support on other variables, and has also mentioned the predictors and outcomes in this case. Flowers et al. (2020) and Afrahi et al. (2021) were followed while reporting content of research question 3.

Small number of studies (n=8) from the reviewed literature has focused on antecedents to spousal support for working population and they are all either personal or work-family related variables. Gender differences was significantly affecting the spousal support offered to working population, it means the support offered relies on the gender of the spouse offering the support. Most of the studies (n=51) are engaged in examining about outcomes for spousal

support and similar to case of antecedents, even consequences for spousal support are personal/individual (e.g., life satisfaction, depression, stress, mental exhaustion) and work-family conflict related. Only few studies (n=4) reported job/organization related consequence (i.e., career achievement measures, career adaptability and turnover intention) as outcome of spousal support. It is of interest to note that 15 studies were focused on understanding effect of spousal support on work-family related outcomes (such as work-family conflict, work-family enrichment). Studies in the literature did not report much variables (n=3) acting as moderators or mediators of spousal support relationship with any outcome/predictor of interest.

Qualitative studies

Part of literature which used qualitative research design has suggested some relationships between spousal support and other independent/dependent variable. Altogether, 8 studies mentioned about possible relationships, where 2 suggested about possible antecedents for spousal support, 2 suggested possible antecedents and consequences and 4 reported about suggested outcomes of spousal support. Even in qualitative studies, majority of the study discussed about consequences of spousal support. Literature suggested gender order, husband's occupation, gender role ideology and marital and socio-cultural dynamics as predictors of spousal support for working population. Interactional marriage contract, wife's psychological contract, career advancement, family related career sense making, women's perception of inequity, work-family conflict, double bind beliefs, women's career success and academic career were mentioned as possible consequences for spousal support. To verify the suggested relations here, empirical study can be conducted on the same in future.

Spousal support as mediator/moderator

An attempt has been made to record and report the studies (see Table 6) where spousal support was not the main focus, but was used as mediator or moderator. In the available literature, 13 studies used spousal support as moderator and 3 studies used it as a mediator. A common observation here is in most of the cases, work-family related variables are used as outcome and individual related are used as predictors. In this case 5 studies used job related variables as predictors (where spousal support are used as moderator).

Table 5: Antecedents, Consequences, Mediators and Moderators in reviewed quantitative articles of Spousal Support (from Quantitative Studies)

Variables	Number of Studies used the variable(s) as....	Example(s)
Antecedents		
Gender differences	2	Zheng X. et al. (2022), Phillips-Miller D.L. et al. (2000).
Multimedia educational intervention, Types of Caregivers, Age differences, Work-linked relationship, Support Preferences-Expectation congruence, Work family conflict and enrichment	1	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Gordon J.R. and Whelan-Berry K.S. (2004), Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2012), O'Brien K.M. et al. (2014).
Consequences		
Work-family conflict	5	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013), Irak, U. D. (2020).
Marital satisfaction	5	Steffy B.D. and Ashbaugh D. (1986), Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2006).
Family-work conflict	6	Aryee S. et al. (1999), Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Irak, U. D. (2020).
Life satisfaction	4	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Irak, U. D. (2020), Aryee S. et al. (1999).
Work-life balance	2	Gordon J.R. and Whelan-Berry K.S. (2004).
Perceived stress	2	Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2006)
Psychological well-being	2	Aycan Z. and Eskin M. (2005).
Emotional exhaustion	2	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2010)
Depression	2	Greenberger E. and O'Neil R. (1993)
Family satisfaction	2	Parasuraman S. et al. (1992).
Career achievement measures	2	Zheng X. et al. (2022).
Work-family enrichment, problem solving effectiveness, inter-role conflict, verbal communication, women's distress level, job satisfaction, career adaptability, turnover intention, role conflict, positive work and family effect, coping mechanism, role strain, anxiety, work family facilitation, role balance, inequity in distribution of household and childcare, double blind beliefs.	1	Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013), Depasquale N. et al. (2018), Suchet M. and Barling J. (1986), Greenberger E. and O'Neil R. (1993), Lee N.Y. et al. (2014).
Mediators		
Work-family balance (between spousal support and career success)	1	Amin S. et al. (2017).
Moderators		
Married co-worker status (moderate relationship between spousal support and coping mechanism)	1	Halbesleben J.R.B. (2010).

Spouse workplace/occupation (moderate between spousal support and emotional exhaustion)	1	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2010).
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Source: Prepared by Author (2020)

Table 6: Study Sample with Spousal Support as Moderator/Mediator

Spousal support used as a moderator between....	Number of studies	Example(s) of Studies
Predictor: Caregiver types Outcomes: Turnover intention and obligation to work while sick	1	Depasquale N. et al. (2018)
Predictor: Inter-role conflict Outcomes: Mental satisfaction and verbal communication	1	Suchet M. and Barling J. (1986)
Predictors: Relational identity Outcomes: Work-family Spillover	1	Polk D.M. (2008)
Predictors: Work hours and autonomy Outcomes: Work-family conflict	1	Noor N.M. (2002)
Predictors: Paternal overload Outcomes: Family work conflict	1	Aryee S. et al. (1999)
Predictors: Family role stressors Outcomes: Life satisfaction	1	Parasuraman S. et al. (1992)
Predictors: Job strain Outcomes: Psychological well being	1	Syrotuik J. and D'Arcy C. (1984)
Predictors: Workplace ostracism Outcomes: Vitality	1	Wang B. et al. (2021)
Predictors: Stressful workplace experience Outcomes: Parenting behaviour	1	Malinen K. et al. (2017)
Predictors: Job and family stress Outcomes: Work-family conflict	1	Westman M. and Da Lia E. (2005)
Predictors: Parental demand Outcomes: Family work conflict	1	Matsui T. et al. (1995)
Predictors: Family supportive supervision Outcomes: Work-family balance	1	Greenhaus J.H. et al. (2012)
Predictors: Wives' Job status Outcomes: Wives' marital instability	1	Byrne A. and Barling J. (2017)
Spousal support used as a mediator between...	Number of Studies	Example(s) of Studies
Predictor: Gender difference Outcomes: Career achievement	1	Zheng X. et al. (2022)
Predictor: Work-linked relationship status Outcomes: Emotional exhaustion	1	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2012)
Predictor: Work-family conflict and enrichment Outcomes: Depression	1	O'Brien K.M. et al. (2014)

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

Methodological Features of Reviewed Literature (Research Question 4)

To answer fourth research question of the literature review, sample characteristics (sample composition and relationship status), sample size, sampling method, data collection method and analytical techniques used in the studies in review has been reported (see Table 7).

(a) Sample Characteristics: In reviewed articles, majority of studies (n =33) included men and women (as couple or otherwise), followed by studies focusing on spousal support for women (n =24). Out of 61 articles, 45 had only married couples, 14 studies were a bit liberal and hence was including married or couple in live in relationship or simply in relationships, and 2 articles considered married or divorced individual as well since they were once married and can share their experience.

(b) Sample size: It should be noted that there were 61 articles but 64 studies, and out of those 64 studies, almost half of the studies had sample size up to 200.

(c) Sampling method: Out of 64 studies, more than half (57 %) did not reported the sampling method used, and in remaining studies most of them were observed using snowball or purposeful sampling. The reason for such a case must be the kind of sample required to study spousal support, you have to purposefully take sample which satisfy criteria of being employed and married (minimum).

(d) Data collection method: While collecting data, most of the studies used questionnaire, followed by interview (especially in case of qualitative study) and only one used interview as well as questionnaire.

(e) Analytical techniques: In this context, regression analysis (such as multiple, hierarchical) was the most common analytical tools to be used (n = 27), followed by correlations (n=10), bootstrapping (n=6), path analysis/SEM (n=6), content analysis (n=5), thematic analysis (n=3), ANOVA (n=3), MANOVA (n=2), analysis of multiple cases (n=2).

Table 7: Summary of Methodological Features of Spousal Support Research

Items	Study used	Percentage	Example(s) of Studies
Sample			
<i>Composition</i>			
Men	4	6.5	Heikkinen, S.S. (2014), Heikkinen S. and Lämsä A.-M. (2017).
Women	24	39	Depasquale N. et al. (2018), Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Nikina A. et al. (2015), Steffy B.D. and Ashbaugh D. (1986), Irak, U. D. (2020).
Both	33	54	Davoine E. et al. (2013), Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013), Bowen P. and Zhang R.P. (2020), Karapinar P. B., et al. (2020), Zheng X. et al. (2022).
<i>Relationship status</i>			
Married	45	73.7	Depasquale N. et al. (2018), Heikkinen, S.S. (2014), Zheng X. et al. (2022), Ahmed S.F. and Carrim N.M.H. (2016).

Married/live in/in relationship	14	23	Parasuraman S. et al. (1992), Halbesleben J.R.B. (2010), Malinen K. et al. (2017), Lee N.Y. et al. (2014).
Married/Divorce	2	3	Thorstad R.R., et al. (2006).
Sample Size			
1-200	33	51.5	Ahmed S.F. and Carrim N.M.H. (2016), Ezzedeen S.R. and Ritchey K.G. (2008), Heikkinen, S.S. (2014), Wani A.K. (2022), Davoine E. et al. (2013).
201-400	15	23	Irak, U. D. (2020), Malinen K. et al. (2017), Phillips-Miller D.L. et al. (2000), Lee N.Y. et al. (2014), Halbesleben J.R.B. (2010).
401-600	9	14	Aryee S. and Luk V. (1996), Aycan Z. and Eskin M. (2005), Van Daalen G. et al. (2006), Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2010).
601-800	5	7.8	Halbesleben J.R.B. et al. (2012), Halbesleben J.R.B. (2010), Bowen P. and Zhang R.P. (2020).
1,956	1	1.5	Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013).
7,764	1	1.5	Zheng X. et al. (2022).
Sampling Method			
Not reported	37	58	Gordon J.R. and Whelan-Berry K.S. (2004), Ocampo A.C.G. et al. (2018), Junker N.M. and van Dick R. (2020), Van Daalen G. et al. (2006).
Snowball/modified snowball	7	11	Irak, U. D. (2020), Ray J.A. (1988), Ezzedeen S.R. and Ritchey K.G. (2008).
Purposeful	7	11	Karapinar P. B., et al. (2020), Ahmed S.F. and Carrim N.M.H. (2016).
Random	7	11	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013).
Convenience	4	6.2	Pluut H. et al. (2006), Bhowon U. et al. (2008).
Experience	1	1.5	Pluut H. et al. (2018)
Systematic random	1	1.5	Syrotuik J. and D'Arcy C. (1984).
Data Collection Method			
Not clear	1	1.6	Pavalko E.K. and Elder G.H., Jr. (1993).
Questionnaire	48	78.6	Noroozi F. et al. (2022), Bowen P. and Zhang R.P. (2020), Aycan Z. and Eskin M. (2005), Amin S. et al. (2017).
Interview	11	18	Nikina A. et al. (2015), Heikkinen, S.S. (2014), Heikkinen S. and Lämsä A.-M. (2017).
Both (Questionnaire and Interview)	1	1.6	Nikina A. et al. (2015).
Analytical Techniques			
Not clear	2	2.7	Pavalko E.K. and Elder G.H., Jr. (1993).
Regression/Hierarchical regression/Seemingly unrelated regression/Stepwise/Multiple regression	27	37.5	Mauno S. and Rantanen M. (2013), Suchet M. and Barling J. (1986), Noor N.M. (2002), Polk D.M. (2008), Aryee S. et al. (1999), Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2003), Bhowon U., et al. (2008).
Correlations	10	14	Ray J.A. (1988), Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2006), Holtzman E.H. and Gilbert L.A. (1987), Bhowon U., et al. (2008).
Path analysis/SEM	6	8.3	Steffy B.D. and Ashbaugh D. (1986), Irak, U. D. (2020).
Bootstrapping (Process Macro)/Bootstrap	6	8.3	Karapinar P. B., et al. (2020), Ocampo A.C.G. et al. (2018).
Content analysis	5	7	Ahmed S.F. and Carrim N.M.H. (2016), Heikkinen S. et al. (2014).
Thematic analysis	3	4	Davoine E. et al. (2013), Mohamed S.F. (2019).
Analysis of multiple cases	2	2.7	Nikina A. et al. (2015)

ANOVA	3	4	Rosenbaum M. and Cohen E. (1999), Junker N.M. and van Dick R. (2020).
MANOVA	2	2.7	Rosenbaum M. and Cohen E. (1999), Kulik L. and Rayyan F. (2006).
Factor analysis, Hotelling T2 Multivariate statistic, Kruskal-Wallis H, Mann-Whitney U-tests and Independent T-tests, SUEST, Textual analysis.	1	8.3	Noor N.M. (2002), Phillips-Miller D.L. et al. (2000), Noroozi F. et al. (2022).

Source: Prepared by Author (2022)

CONCLUSION

The current review aims to scope the literature relating to spousal support offered to working population in dealing with everyday hassles of managing work and life. In this review, only those articles have been included where spousal support provided to working class have been examined and not what support working class can provide to their partners. To allow a broader coverage, articles from all the disciplines were included as working population and the support offered to them can be studied in any discipline. Altogether, 61 papers were identified in the relevant topic with relevant population. Because of the focus of study, only married (or in relationship) and employed individuals were considered. There was a particular focus on working women in the literature and it is to be mentioned that more or less this report prepared is based on Western culture, as majority of studies were from USA, or European countries. This result is similar to observation made by Heikkinen (2014) and it suggests the need of more active involvement of non-western countries in the field. The literature acquired indicates that work on the topic of spousal support in context of working population has not started in recent years, in fact the first study on the topic was published in 1984 by J. Syrotuik and C. D'Arcy. A major limitation of the realized literature is not providing original definition for spousal support, only 3 out of 61 studies were found providing a detailed definition of spousal support. One was provided by Aycaan, Z. and Eskin, M. (2005), he defined it as “help, advice, understanding, and the like that spouses provide for one another.”. Second, Greenberger, E. and O'Neil, R. (1993) defined spousal support as “support from spouse that reflects the degree to which respondents feel that their spouse offers support for their activities and needs in the roles of parent and paid worker.” Third definition was provided by Kim and Ling (2001), according to them “spouse support is mostly mental, with attitude support the greatest, followed by emotional, childcare and housework.” Moreover, theoretical and methodological limitation were observed in the literature, as a greater number of studies did not mention sampling method

or industry, they collected data from. Also, most of them failed to mention and utilize any theoretical framework to explain spousal support.

An important observation made in the review is that there is no universal measurement scale for spousal support. Family supply inventory scale and majority of the other scales used in the studies were modified version of social support scale. More importantly, among the small number of studies (n=4) on spousal support for working men, only one study proposed a scale measuring spousal support for working men (Syrotuik, J. and D'Arcy, C. ,1984), 3 of them utilized qualitative data. Wherever mix samples (men and women) were taken, a common spousal support scale was used where items were more or less focused on spousal support for women.

Focusing on the variables studied in relation with spousal support (in qualitative and quantitative studies), it can be stated that majority of studies has made personal or work-family related variables as their centre of attention. Even though studies selected here has examined spousal support in context with working population, but it is non-work-related variables or work-family issues which has been in limelight.

For subsequent literature review, it is suggested to cover other databases with focus on highly relevant studies (i.e., whose main focus is on spousal support). In context of population, occupation and working hours for sample should also be reported as their occupation can have an effect on extent of spousal support offered. Review articles in future should remember that spousal support is being reported by the person receiving support in some cases and in other it is reported by person providing the support. Apart from the fact that what support does spouse gives to working population, certain studies may focus on support provided by working class. This kind of variation should be specified or dealt with, in upcoming reviews. Spousal support can be different for heterogenous and homogenous couples, hence, a comparison through literature review can validate the facts.

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